

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TILAHUN****FIRST NAME: GEZAHEGN G.****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Writing a good essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Some rules of thumb for writing a good essay (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

As I am from a country where non-native speakers of the English language, this course of academic essays is interesting and engaging to improve my skill in writing and communicating arguments effectively. This course highlights how to research, organize and write evidence-backed arguments briefly with standard structures and other elements, particularly in professional settings. It also addressed the impact of plagiarism in our work and established mechanisms to avoid plagiarism and acknowledge others' work.

In this response paper, I discuss the steps and contents of academic writing. The rules that are required to follow for effective academic writing and proper citations are also discussed in this paper. In addition, this paper discusses the English language variants among American and British, the importance of style guides, and avoiding plagiarism while writing an academic paper.

2) WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

An academic essay analyzes and briefly presents evidence on a specific subject of interest or argument. Generally, there are steps to follow and consider to write an effective academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Writing a good essay requires dedicating adequate time. Getting started with the task of developing an essay as soon as possible helps to have more time to read, research, analyze, and write on the topic of interest and answer the questions. This includes avoiding procrastination while undertaking essay writing which benefits a writer to commit more time to the task. Identifying and understanding the questions and tasks that must be addressed when writing an essay on a research topic is also essential. In addition, setting a plan for how to write an essay gives and guides how to complete the tasks successfully (EUCLID 2021, 7).

An academic essay comprises three structures: introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction section covers information like a short topic orientation. It also answers the question with a thesis statement and briefly explains what will be covered in each part of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10).

The body of the academic essay discusses the main ideas of the research topics to answer the question by gathering, analyzing, and interpreting relevant evidence (EUCLID 2021, 10). In the conclusion section, the writers summarize their main points or arguments and conclude with the implication of their paper (EUCLID 2021, 10).

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

EUCLID suggests rules of thumb that guide the writer to develop a successful paper. Some of the rules are discussed below.

The main point of the thesis needs to be reflected at the beginning of the sentences. This facilitates the readers to catch the idea of the argument from the start and get motivated to continue with the reading. While writing, the author also needs to focus on specific issues that he would like to discuss and answer the questions. In addition, the author should write clearly and keep different types of sentence constructions as appropriate (EUCLID 2021, 13).

Keeping away from a statement that leads to generalization is also required while writing a paper. Doing so will help avoid overlooking the value of our task. Again, if the writers wish to contribute to someone's assertion in their task, they need to provide evidence to the view of the assertion (EUCLID 2021, 14).

Prevention of plagiarism is key to consider while writing a paper. If the writers incorporate someone's idea, the source should be acknowledged. This can be done by taking the full words in the quotation or paraphrasing the idea with detail of references about the sources of information at the end of the paper (EUCLID 2021, 14).

4) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

American and British English are the two widely known variants of the English language, with more similarities than differences. Their differences commonly occur in spelling, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar (EUCLID 21, 25). Knowing their difference and sticking with one of them is essential to be consistent throughout our academic writing.

Among the variation between the two languages is pronunciation differences of the same word with the same spelling. Advertisement, controversy, laboratory, schedule, and secretary are some examples with the same spelling but pronounced differently in the US and UK. Spelling variation with the same pronunciation also occurs in some instances. For example, US English uses "center," "color," and "ax," while UK English uses "centre" "colour," and "axe" (EUCLID 21, 25).

In addition, vocabulary also varies between the two languages. There are words which are the same spelling with different or additional meanings. For example, Corn is "maize" or "sweetcorn" in the US, while it is "any cereal" or "wheat," is in GB (EUCLID 21, 26).

Furthermore, the usage of periods, commas, and quotation marks varies across the two languages in some instance. British English uses 'inverted commas' while American English uses "quotation marks" to indicate speech or a quote within a text. In addition, the period and comma can be used inside or outside closing quotation marks in GB, while they are always inside closing quotation marks in the US (EUCLID 21, 31-32). Punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives are other differences between the two languages.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that information (EUCLID 2021, 34). In an academic paper, it is compulsory to indicate the sources if someone's work or idea is utilized to support our work.

Plagiarism can be prevented by appropriately citing the source of information in our scientific paper. Citation is a method of recognizing the work of others that is utilized in our work to advance our arguments. In addition, it locates the reader to access the source document and validate the author's content against the original author. Moreover, it is an opportunity to illustrate the connection of our work with other works and ideas conducted in the past (NC State University, n.d).

In-text citation with a corresponding reference list at the end of the paper is one of the citation methods used in scientific papers (EUCLID 2021, 34). The in-text citation is used in the body of the paper to briefly indicate the sources of quotations and paraphrasing utilized in our work. The list of cited references complements in-text citations and is

provided at the end of the paper with detailed information about the sources of information (EUCLID 2021, 34).

6) A STYLE GUIDE

Consistency of writing style is a key feature of a scientific paper. Many companies have their own rules and standards to ensure consistency across documents written by writers. EUCLID (2021, 41) defines a style guide as a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of a writing style that needs to be consistent. A style guide defines the standards and instructions that need to be followed while a writer develops content for a specific publication or company. Some elements that need consistency are layout, structure, sentence length, font, grammar, acronyms, etc (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

A style guide aids a writer in maintaining consistency in branding and messaging. It also makes it easier for several authors to work together to create content. In addition, it allows readers to get comfortable and navigate through the content of documents easily (Purdue university, n.d.). There are different guide styles in an academic institute. EUCLID (2021, 41) suggests applying Chicago (Turabian) and American English rules for our works, although other international rules are acceptable.

7) CONCLUSION

I am excited to begin my Ph.D. journey with EUCLID University. A new endeavor is always hard at the beginning till the right way is found and adjusted to the way to get there. This first session helps me prepare well for subsequent courses that are expected to require new skills and perseverance to make progress.

In this first course, I find that how is significant to improve my writing skill to communicate my idea or thought effectively. In this first response paper, I am challenged by my writing abilities which should be cultivated regularly to deal with similar tasks. I find also that regularly applying the recommended rules, citations, and styles of writing a paper is key to maintain the appropriate consistency and quality of the outcomes.

REFERENCES

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Purdue University. n.d. "Style Guide Overview - Purdue OWL®." Accessed April 10, 2023b. https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/avoiding_plagiarism/guide_overview%20.html.

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